

Educational Funding Intervention Management and Manpower Development in Tertiary Institutions: Exploring the University of Nigeria

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Abstract

Tertiary education in Nigeria has witnessed a sharp decline in funding following the proliferation of public and private universities in the 1970s and 1980s. The establishment of Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in 2011 and its objectives of ameliorating the challenges of funding and enhancing key areas of infrastructure and research development have become a major font of debate among scholars. This study interrogates the disconnect between funding intervention and manpower development, using the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus as a study area, and adopting a multi-layered qualitative approach that combined the essential features of key informant interview (KII), focused group discussions, field observations reports and documentary evidence. Embracing the basic assumptions of Institutional Corruption Theory, the study found that TETFund intervention disbursement in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus, lacks transparency, and therefore recommends a more transparent-meritorious means of fund intervention disbursement and prioritizing staff development programmes.

Keywords: *Tertiary Institution, Intervention Funding, Manpower Development, Infrastructural Development, University of Nigeria.*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of funding and its significant contribution to development cannot be overemphasized. As a concept of universal importance, funding can be explored from various units of social, political, and economic compositions. Be it organisational, institutional and inter-governmental relations, funding interventions have remained essential in facilitating accelerated development across the globe. Interventions, however, originates from different sponsorship, ranging from government direct interventions to critical institutions, voluntary funding from nongovernmental organisations, and certain levels of funding sponsorships from private organisations and local groups. In the organisational and institutional structures, funding has encouraged productivity in the aspects of infrastructure development, promotions, and most importantly, manpower development.

However, manpower development which depends primarily on employee training, incentive packages, and a positive work environment is essential to institutional stability, and a significant factor in high productivity. These qualities of personnel development are crucial for the efficacy and growth of higher institutions (universities), although they are also necessary for organizational outputs. Increasing staff productivity, as a critical component of financial interventions for manpower development in tertiary institutions, has been a hot topic

among academics, particularly because of its significance in promoting high-level academic and social effect on students.

Since the inception of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, funding has primarily been the government's responsibility through allocations and the implementation of the Education Trust Fund under the 1993 Education Tax Decree, supplemented by tuition fees and minor internally generated revenues within the universities. According to Abdulkareem, Fasasi, and Akinnubi (2011), Nigeria established higher educational institutions in order to supply the country with graduates who would work in a variety of capacities to support the political and socioeconomic growth of the country. Nevertheless, due to conflicting demands from other sectors, the Nigerian government has not been able to satisfy the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) proposal of allocating to the education sector 26% of the entire budget (Echono, 2024). Moreover, government efforts to support these schools were overtaken by population growth and the expansion of state universities, controlled by the government in the 1970s, followed by polytechnics in the 1980s and 1990s. As of January 2024, there were 262 accredited universities in Nigeria, including 52 Federal Universities, 63 State Universities, and 147 Private Universities (National Universities Commission, NUC, 2024). Additionally, 236 Nigerian institutions that are held by the federal, state, and private sectors have been listed by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) as NCE Awarding Institutions. 183 Federal, State, and Privately Owned Polytechnics, 84 Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs), 227 Monotechnics, and 181 Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs) have received accreditation from the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (Echono, 2024).

Onuoha (2013), Rasheed (2019), Taiwo (1980) Okigbo (1981) noted that this proliferation of tertiary institutions invariably affected manpower productivity, as many university administration could not cope with the rising number of students with limited academic staff to ensure effective teaching and application of learning curriculum, followed by lack of maintenance of office facilities, sporting facilities, recreational centres within the school environs, building new student hostels and effective management of old student hostels. As a consequence of the above challenges, the quality of Nigerian universities started to witness a speedy decline as a result of reduced/inconsistency in funding, culminating to gross manpower development decline and increase brain drain, shortage of skilled labour, low academic research inputs, poor student preparation, etc (Ogar, 2012; Adesina & Awonusi, 2004; Ogunde, 2011; Okebukola, 2002; Aluede, 2012; Okuwa, 2004) Most universities funding channels were principally inadequate, and accumulation of facilities that required maintenance kept increasing.

These also introduced certain level of corruption and mismanagement of funds. In an effort to guarantee the transformation of public tertiary institutions, the Federal Government of Nigeria established the Tertiary Education Trust Fund in 2011 to offer intervention support for the consolidation, restoration, and rehabilitation of tertiary education in the country. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), which replaced the Educational Trust Fund of 1993, focused on improving the quality of education in Nigeria by funding short and long term tertiary programmes, staff training and development, and project facilitation. According to the statute that established the Fund, all Nigerian registered firms' earnings must be subject to an education tax of 2 percent, which is currently 3 percent. Fifty percent of the funds are distributed to universities, twenty-five percent to polytechnics, and twenty-five percent to colleges of education (TETFund Act, 2011).

With a focus on the unmeritorious tendencies of fund disbursement, this study investigates the various aspects of TETFund interventions and their impacts on manpower development. It does this by cross-examining issues of disbursement and the dynamics of funding academic staff welfare packages and development programs in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus. The study's significance anchors on the importance of institutional and organizational openness, as well as the present financing intervention program in Nigerian institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Without considering its natural resources, Nigeria, which has a population of over 215 million and the highest young demographic among many countries worldwide, can sustain a stable economy and utilize its potential in research and education. The nation has seen the worst socioeconomic indicators, including low life expectancy, poverty, unemployment, high infant mortality, and, most regrettably, low school enrolment and poor education quality, despite this enormous opportunity (Okonta, 2025; Udeogu & Ogenyi, 2024). Numerous academics have debated various complex reasons and potential solutions to these problems, hinging their arguments mostly on the idea that the Nigerian educational system should be revived starting with the most fundamental levels of primary school education while others disagree, arguing that university education is the pinnacle of effective education and should take precedence. Arising partly from the foregoing debate and partly from the recognized institutional cum structural collapse occasioned by poor funding, are two perspectives to the debate on funding interventions. These are the Instrumentalist perspective and the Structuralist perspective.

The instrumentalist scholars view tertiary education as a tool and a primary source of economic development. In the words of Rosowsky (2022), universities all over the world have remained the basic centres of research, learning and development of critical areas of medicine, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, engineering, politics, governance, etc., while engaging services of outreach as core elements and objectives of university education. Furthermore, Asoya and Chukwuemeka (2023); Emmanuel et al (2025); Igbokwe et al (2024); Ikhenoba et al (2023); Davlembayeva and Alamanos (2025); Zehra (2024); UK Innovation Report (2025), Universities Uk (2025), Tiyas and Imronudin (2025); Seliti et al (2025), Modester Peter Mgeta (2025); Kumera et al (2024); Kaviya and Balakrishnan (2025); Kuknor and Kumar (2024); Kafetzopoulos et al (2024); Joanna, Sumit and Manuel (2024); Mabrouk (2024); Muhammad (2025); Heba (2025); Khalid (2025); Devlin (2024); Czerny and Letmathe (2024); Buberwa et al (2024); Bahrumisyah (2023); American Psychological Association (2025) supported claims that every tertiary institution's exceptional performance is primarily reliant on its ability to provide the necessary manpower, training, and support to achieve the desired output, while noting that an organization's capacity to provide its employees with regular training and retraining is a compelling requirement for both the achievement of organizational goals and the effective delivery of services. Building an employee's capacity inside an organization is similar to honing an artisan's tools; it involves improving the abilities required for creativity, innovation, and responsiveness to demands in the global workforce.

Additionally, they argued that another intervention avenue, particularly from the TETFund intervention initiatives, is conference participation. The Fund provides funding for academic employees from public postsecondary institutions to attend conferences both domestically and abroad in an effort to improve their research abilities and put them on level with their international counterparts. The conference can take many various forms, including

trade conferences, news conferences, professional conferences, business conferences, and academic conferences.

Evidently, the purpose of conferences is to develop various learning tools, including workshops, panel discussions, and lectures. By giving them the chance to collaborate with peers and learn about new technologies and trends, it also gives academic staff members a way to further their careers. It enables these individuals to engage with peers worldwide and gain firsthand exposure to and experience in both local and international settings in their various fields and areas of study. These scholars came to the conclusion that, when appropriately utilized, tertiary education and research represent cutting-edge frontiers of both national and international development, and serve as a means of facilitating interregional researcher partnerships.

The structuralist scholars, on the other hand, focus on the evaluation of the institutional failure and structural collapse of vital development organs, attributing it to wide range of issues. Mela et al (2024); Ezekwe and Ani (2024); Ogunode et al (2024); Ananyi and Ufomba-Emeka (2023); Nkem and Emma (2023); Niyi and Gregory (2023); Sani (2023); Solomon (2024); Aguke and Igbomor (2024); Arubayi and Igbomor (2024); Udeogu et al (2024); Bolanle et al (2025); Nnenna and Ejiofor (2024); Nzimakwe and Utete (2024); Retorio (2025) examined these issues and viewpoints, concluding that staff development is primarily focused on enhancing, updating, and preserving employees' skills and abilities through conference attendance, journal publications, and other research and infrastructure development. They noted that, on the one hand, most staff members lack the requisite skills, particularly ICT-compliant knowledge and experience, as a result of the educational system's corruption and incompetence. They claim that ICT-based training has lately become more well-known worldwide.

The initiative has expanded to include the intellectual and educational potential of numerous European nations as well as China and Kenya. However, Nigeria has not been able to fully exploit these aspects of learning, particularly when it comes to the adoption of e-learning. Furthermore, they noted that one of the main issues plaguing Nigerian tertiary education throughout the years has been a lack of personnel. With a large outflow of university instructors (brain drain) to foreign institutions with better working circumstances, the resulting effects on teaching, learning, and other tertiary education system components are concerning. From the structuralist and instrumentalist viewpoints, this paper examines the arguments made by academics on higher education (university) premise, as well as the conflicting discussions of these two schools of thought around funding interventions and manpower development.

Nigerian public institutions have an absurd lecturer-to-student ratio as a result of the personnel crisis. Inconsistent plans and policies have been caused by political instability, which has made matters worse. The orientation, emphasis, timing, and method of high-quality research have suffered as a result of this and the regular disruptions to the academic calendar caused by strikes or other needless closures. Basic facilities, including labs, tools and equipment, internet access, etc. are either nonexistent or in poor condition in many universities. The poor and deteriorating welfare of academic staff at Nigeria's public institutions is another concern on tertiary education in the country, as academic staff members find it difficult and discouraging to pursue further degrees and attend conferences on their own dime. The high degree of nepotism and the absence of clear procedures for choosing competent employees have equally rendered TETFund's intervention attempts ineffective, even though the

organization was founded in 2011 with the intention of enhancing research and infrastructure development.

Academics at Nigeria's higher education institutions lack the ability to do substantial research, even when it is accessible. Many instructors at universities, polytechnics, and education institutions lack the fundamental aptitude, and drive to do quality research in a variety of subjects. Due to their inability, they are equally disadvantaged in obtaining grants or research funding from both within and outside of their schools. Lack of timely and reliable data, absence of research-related legal frameworks, low adoption and application of research findings, academic corruption, including lengthy postgraduate student supervision, and low computer literacy among scholars all exacerbate the situation (Immaculata & Victoria, 2023).

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the theory of institutional corruption. The theory of institutional corruption is a developed conception on corruption that differs from that of conventional corruption in both its individual and structural forms. The theory was developed by Thompson, Dennis F. in his book “Ethics in Congress: From Individual to Institutional Corruption”, in 2000. Although Thompson suggests that his conception can be applied broadly to a wide variety of institutions, government and society, his early works on the theory focuses almost exclusively on the US Congress, and more on the internal procedures than on the campaign finance system (Thompson 2000).

Scholars such as Warren (2004), Miller (2010, 2017) and Lessig (2011) have also in different perspectives, further contributed to the development of the theory. Despite the different perspectives of the theory, the key and the most important theoretical foundation of the whole concept is the argument of the proponents (i.e. Thompson, Warren, Miller and Lessig), that corruption is distinctively integral to an institution in three ways:

- First, it is equivocal: The corruption benefits the institution while undermining it. The corruption exploits legitimate institutional practices that provide benefits that even an uncorrupted institution needs, and for which alternatives must be found if the institution is to function well.
- Second, institutional corruption is impersonal: The individual agents of corruption act in institutional roles and do not have the corrupt motives that characterize agents who participate in quid pro quo exchanges.
- Third, the corruption is generalizable: It is found not only in government but in many other kinds of institutions.

Lessig (2011), summarized the basic component of the institutional corruption framework as an economy of influence that weakens the effectiveness of an institution, especially by weakening public trust of that institution. The theory brings in the social context and provides a taxonomy for understanding how corruption might become entrenched in organizations, and society, despite an anti-corruption framework (Lou, 2005).

The institutional corruption framework considers that corruption influences the political system's character, design, transparency and institutions. It further advances that corruption exists on individual and institutional levels and that both levels undercut the performance of government policies.

The institutional conception of corruption by the proponents of this theory stems from the argument that first, the conception brings out more clearly how corruption is related to the theory and practice of the institutions in which it is embedded. In the case of political institutions, institutionalists connect the corruption to principles of democratic theory. They emphasize that, while developed democracies may have reduced the incidence of conventional corruption, they are prone to their own kind of corruption, which may be more insidious.

Second, their conception supports efforts to broaden the reach of legal and ethical regulation. It is used to challenge the view, currently held by the US Supreme Court that corruption refers only to quid pro quo exchanges and to revive the more expansive view held by the Founders and earlier legal thinkers (Teachout 2014, pp. 32–55, 227–45). The institutional conception also clarifies and reinforces the rationale for regulating appearances of corruption and conflicts of interest. Third, the conception enables more appropriate and more precise targeting of reforms. It shifts the focus from deterring and removing corrupt individuals (acting alone or systematically) to changing the rules and procedures of the institution and the incentives for individuals who may not be corrupt. Although most of the institutionalists focus on political institutions, all suggest that their theories can be extended. Hence, other scholars tend to examine institutional corruption in a wide variety of contexts. More so, Tycho (2017) cautioned that institutional theory of corruption is still undergoing refinement and sophistication. Therefore, its application to any context should be cautiously done.

Application of the Theory

The theoretical assumption of institutional corruption theory is suitable to this study in that it explains:

- How the manifestation of corruption at both institutional and individual levels undermine the impact and performance of governance. Incidents of corruption at the individual level and institutional level are a clog on the process and output of governance.
- How the connection between types of corruption is tied to the function of the institution or policy involved. There is a strong link between the forms of corruption and the functions of policies and institutions.
- The connection between impacts of corruption and its effects on individuals, policies and institutions are mutually reinforcing.

The relevance of the theory of institutional corruption to this study is to basically unearth and explain the reason for the continued problem of decadence in tertiary institutions in Nigeria despite the increased annual allocations made by government. The theory of institutional corruption in this context, basically offers a justification for the continued existence of corruption within the institutions and actors involved in Civil Service, which disrupts the target which is prudent management, greater accountability and transparency. Drawing from the theory, it could be understood that the factors bedeviling the tertiary institutions in Nigeria includes nepotism, discrimination and racketeering.

Explaining within the theoretical lens of institutional corruption, it can easily be deduced that even with the annual expenditures made by tertiary institutions; the institutions is designed in such a way that corruption exploits legitimate institutional practices that provide benefits to the institutions while undermining them. This explains the reason why even when there is continued paucity in the implementation of the expenses made by government punitive measures are hardly meted on them. Also, even when there is individual level of corruption

within the institutions involved in the Public Service in Enugu State, individual agents in these institutions mostly act in institutional roles, and thus are far from the reach of legal and ethical regulations. Despite laws, reforms, frameworks adopted and enacted for the promotion of Tertiary education development, the design of educational funding interventions and the integral corruption within these institutions weakens its effectiveness and influences the performance.

EMPIRICAL DISCOURSE AND ANALYTICAL DISPOSITION OF TETFUND INTERVENTION AND MANPOWER DEVELOPMENT IN THE UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA, NSUKKA CAMPUS

Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) has carried out various functions to assist in re-positioning the University system of education to an enviable height. Although a landmark is yet to be made in re-positioning the university system nationwide, some level of achievements have been made given the impact of the monitoring and coordinating functions of the organisation. TETFund has been responsible for the distribution of intervention funds to the various public higher institutions in Nigeria. This includes the Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and other levels of education. As an intervention agency, it has been responsible for ensuring that the objectives of the public tertiary institutions in the country are met through the provision of necessary resources (Luke & Pius, 2021). Nevertheless, little can be attributed to the intervention of TETFund in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus as staff compliance on its effectiveness to the development of research and general concerns of manpower growth are yet to be achieved. This section analyses with concrete data the contribution of TETFund between 2017 and 2025, outlining the various concerns of staff over key aspects of welfare and development capacity, its position and effect in the development of manpower productivity through the following tables:

Table 1: University of Nigeria Staff Strength Data

UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA, STAFF DATA OF ACADEMICS AND NON ACADEMICS			
S/NO	FACULTY	ACADEMICS	NON-ACADEMICS
1.	AGRIC	183	172
2.	ARTS	300	162
3.	BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES	70	58
4.	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE S	156	138
5.	BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION	114	55
6.	DENTISTRY	28	37
7.	EDUCATION	314	117
8.	ENGINEERING	203	197
9.	ENVIRONMENT STUDIES	81	51
10.	HEALTH SCIENCES	117	60
11.	LAW	41	47
12.	CLINICAL SCIENCES	257	129
13.	PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES	115	103
14.	PHYSICAL SCIENCES	245	190
15.	SOCIAL SCIENCES	354	119
16.	VETINARY MEDICINE	120	119
17.	VOCATIONAL TECHNICAL EDUCATION	80	96
TOTAL		2,778	1,850
GRAND TOTAL		4,628	

Source: Data retrieved from Academic Planning Unit, University of Nigeria and compiled by the authors (2025).

Table 1: catalogues of the entire staff strength of the University of Nigeria across all faculties of learning and administrative units of the institution.

Table 2: University of Nigeria, Nsukka Campus Staff Strength Data

UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA, STAFF DATA OF ACADEMICS AND NON ACADEMICS, NSUKKA CAMPUS			
S/NO	FACULTY	ACADEMICS	NON-ACADEMICS
1.	AGRIC	183	172
2.	ARTS	300	162
3.	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE S	156	138
4.	EDUCATION	314	117
5.	ENGINEERING	203	197
6.	PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES	115	103
7.	PHYSICAL SCIENCES	245	190
8.	SOCIAL SCIENCES	354	119
9.	VETINARY MEDICINE	120	119
10.	VOCATIONAL TECHNICAL EDUCATION	80	96
TOTAL		2,070	1,413
GRAND TOTAL		3,483	

Source: Data retrieved from Academic Planning Unit, University of Nigeria and compiled by the authors (2025).

Table 2: Data on staff strength as compiled motivated the sourcing of relevant data on the categories of intervention and the number of staff that have benefited from TETFund Interventions from 2017 to 2025 as represented in table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Tertiary Education Trust Fund approved year intervention budget, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. 2017 t0 2025

Year and Total Amount of all projects intervention funding and budget. 2017 to 2025.		Selected interventions on staff development programmes and allocated amount		
YEAR	Total Amount (₦)	Academic staff training & development	Conference Attendance	Institution Based Research
2017	659,150,000.00	120,000,000.00	30,000,000.00	25,000,000.00
2018	756,674,600.00	300,000,000.00	26,000,000.00	20,000,000.00
2019	826,684,392.00	150,000,000.00	45,000,000.00	30,000,000.00
2020	906,861,920.67	156,000,000.00	20,000,000.00	50,000,000.00
2021	906,861,920.67	156,000,000.00	20,000,000.00	50,000,000.00
2022	642,848,138	-	-	-
2023	1,154,732,133	-	-	-
2024	1,906,944,930	-	-	-
2025	2,860,562,352.66	-	-	-

Source: Tertiary Education Trust Fund TETFund Approved Intervention Budget 2010-2025.

Table 3 however is represented in Figure 1

Figure 1: Budget Intervention Distribution Funds in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. 2017-2025

Source: compiled by the author (2025); with data collected from TETFund Approved Intervention Budget. 2010-2025

Table 4: TETFund Interventions and Staff Beneficiary Indices of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. 2017-2025

TETFUND INTERVENTIONS AND STAFF BENEFICIARY INDICES 2017-2025				
Major TETFund interventions	Interventions sought by staff between 2017-2025	Number of Staff who applied between 2017-2025	Number of Staff who benefited between 2017-2025	Year 2017-2025
Academic Staff Training and Development (AST&D)	Academic Staff Training and Development (AST&D)	Data Not available	74	2017-2025
Academic Manuscript Development	Academic Manuscript Development	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
Conference Attendance	Conference Attendance	Data Not available	447	2018-2024
Institutional Based Research	Institutional Based Research	Data Not available	156	2021-2024
Academic Research Journal	Academic Research Journal	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
National Research Fund	National Research Fund	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
ICT Support	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
Academic Research Journal	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
Academic Manuscript Development	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available
Library Development	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available	Data Not available

Source: TETFund Secretariat, University of Nigeria, Nsukka and compiled by the authors (2025).

It can be deduced from **Table 4** that interventions, such as Academic Staff Training and Development (AST&D), recorded no data on the number of staff who applied between 2017 and 2025, but recorded 74 recipients of the interventions within the same year. Conference attendance recorded 447 recipients, while institutional based research intervention recording 156 recipients with no data on the number of staff who applied between 2017 and 2025. Other interventions - Academic Manuscript Development, Academic Research Journal, National Research Fund, and Academic Research Journal recorded no data for both number of staff who applied and received from 2017 to 2025. It is on this premise that we interviewed the Director of TETFund, University of Nigeria, as presented in **Table 5**, to gain more insight into the situation concerning intervention in the University.

Table 5: Correspondence with the Director TETFund, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

INTERVIEW WITH DIRECTOR OF TETFUND.		
S/N	QUESTIONS	RESPONSES
1	There have been questions surrounding the disbursement of TETFund, and many staff members of the University have been saying that it is very hard for them to access TETFund benefits?	First, let me denounce that notion. It is not hard to get TETFund intervention, as long as you observe all the guidelines, but you should know that TETFund is competitive. It is a limited fund, needed by so many people but then once you do things correctly, you stand a chance of accessing the intervention. I need to state clearly that there are five interventions in TETFund: Staff Training and Development (ST&D), Infrastructural Development. Under staff development, we have conference intervention, IBR institution Based Research, Manuscript Development, Faculty Based Journal. So, usually, people don't apply; most times it has to do with information. We, at this level, have tried to conscientise people through various means, such as sending notices to staff emails, etc.
2	Are there specific ways your department provides monitoring to those who succeeded to gain the intervention, to see if they are actually utilizing the intervention properly to achieve what they are meant for?	Yes, every funding has got Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E). TETFund at the central level also monitors funding to different schools, and the host institutions also monitor Institutional Based Research. One of the measures is ensuring that staff applying for IBR is at least two or more to avoid cases concerning health challenges or any form of absenteeism. So, we encourage team work to encourage efficiency and credibility. We also adopt measures of visiting the beneficiary at least once during the duration of the research, to ensure that what is being requested for is actually what is being carried out. We also insist on a publication or a documentation of that research project within the timeframe of the research. We also have a robust monitoring on Manuscript Development, making sure that they are published by the university press and also deposited at the national library. For conferences, we adopt strict measures for attendees. You must present your certificate of attendance and a pictorial evidence of your participation in the conference. In some cases, you are expected to present your bus ticket or flight ticket, boarding pass, your stamp in and stamp out visa. The difficult part remains cases of those that are on foreign sponsorship, most of whom after experiencing the country overseas don't really want to come back to the country. Before, we do have about 5% of persons who choose not to come back, but now we do have about 95% of staff

		beneficiaries who naturally don't want to come back to the country. This has made possible for TETFUND at the national level to stop the foreign sponsorships, but we are still very much challenged by the same factor.
3	How does the university get this TETFUND Infrastructural interventions? Are they still under your office?	TETFund allocates funds to universities every year. We have annual interventions and special interventions, zonal interventional. It maybe a building, furniture, office equipment, revitalisation of old infrastructures, etc. When the funds are not enough for the project, the university usually allows it to accumulate, that's when you see merged projects such 2020/2021 merged TETFund interventions, for example. These interventions are mostly statutory.
4	Is it also possible for TETFUND to also involve in road construction, renovation of the sports complex, etc?	No, they can only be involved in those kinds of project when it is proven beyond every reasonable doubt that those infrastructures will contribute effectively and immensely to academic and research purposes.
5	Finally, Sir, do students benefit from TETFUND?	Students benefit indirectly, when classrooms are built, and offices for lecturers are well provided to encourage the needed environment for learning, but TETFUND does not directly fund student related affairs.

Source: Interview with the Director of TETFUND, University of Nigeria (2025)

The foregoing interviews transcripts on **Table 5** make it clear that TETFund interventions must be implemented in a variety of manpower development areas, including conference attendance, individual and group research development, and infrastructure improvements to increase academic staff productivity and, consequently, that of other university administrative staff. The availability and transparency of it, however, have become hot topics of discussion among many University of Nigeria faculty and personnel.

Based on the aforementioned claims, the respondent, who holds the position of director of the University's TETFund, clarified that the government does, in fact, regularly fund universities in the areas of staff training and development (ST&D) and infrastructure development.

He also mentioned that there have been several attempts to encourage and conscientize university staff to take advantage of the opportunities in the TETFund, but he disclosed that strict adherence to the application guidelines for intervention is necessary to ensure a smooth process.

He reiterated the university's commitment to developing, motivating, and encouraging staff training and infrastructure research development, acknowledging that the majority of personnel do not adhere to the established parameters and are thus not chosen to benefit from the interventions.

It is no debate from the above analysis that proper manpower development is the bedrock of national development and progress. Ajonuma (2010), Olaniyan and Ojo (2008), Ogunode (2020), Ameen and Hanif (2013), Ajonuma (2010), Ejumudo (2014), Alaba (2021), Okotoniand Erero (2005), Asiyai (2015), Onyenemezu (2012), Isaac and Haastrup (2012), argued that training continues to be a special instrument for developing and promoting employee skills and maintaining skilled human capital, which is the cornerstone for raising organizational effectiveness, productivity, and efficiency. They also noted that the calibre and

number of qualified employees impact institutions' or organization's productivity and ability to provide services effectively.

Tertiary education institutions must thus work to train and develop their human capital to be innovative, creative, and inventive in order to improve their efficiency and effectiveness, as well as to give them a competitive edge over their peers, if they are to survive in today's knowledge-driven and competitive economic society. They contended that while physical buildings and equipment are essentially required, they can only be used as supplementary resources in educational institutions.

The most productive capital in any institution will continue to be human resources, as no school can perform better than its workforce, which is essential to achieving its goals and missions. In summary, they came to the conclusion that the development of manpower is an essential component of the nation's economic, political, scientific, and socio-cultural transition. The most important resource must thus be mobilized to support and guarantee progress in all facets of national growth.

The results of the focused group discussion, however, run counter to the TETFund director's stance and arguments as documented on **Table 5**. The following questions and conversations were recorded during the group discussion of 50 academic staff that were chosen at random and divided into five groups across the 10 departments of the University of Nigeria's Nsukka campus:

- 1) Have you tried applying for TETFund intervention. If no, why have you not applied? The responses to this question revealed that out of 50 staff involved in the discussion, 23 have not applied, 27 have applied, while 5 among the 27 acknowledged they are beneficiaries to the intervention.
- 2) Can you say majority of academic staff in Nsukka campus are beneficiaries of direct TETFund interventions individually? The responses to this question revealed that out of 50 staff interviewed, 13 responses were positive to the question, 30 responses negative, while 7 responses commented nothing on the question.
- 3) TETFund intervention goal is to improve the quality of the university and encourage manpower development. Can you say the intervention has achieved these aims? From the data gathered, 29 responses strongly negated the idea of TETFund interventions as improving manpower development. Whereas 16 responses acknowledged its successful impact, 5 responses commented nothing to the question.
- 4) Do you think TETFund intervention in the university is politicized or based on merit? From the data gathered, 38 responses strongly agreed that TETFund intervention in the university is politicized, 8 responses maintained it has been on merit, while 4 responses commented nothing on the question.
- 5) What are the areas you think these interventions can pay more attention to encourage manpower development? The responses obtained revealed that 10 responses recommended improved postgraduate programmes sponsorships for young academia, 6 responses supported improved conference attendance, 4 responses recommended foreign sponsorship programmes, 4 responses supported training and workshop, 8 responses agreed to improved building and infrastructure projects, 4 responses indicated more employment of staff, while 21 responses strongly recommended improved research development and grants to staff.

Figure 2: Expression of Responses to Group Discussions

Source: Focused Group Discussion (2025).

Figure 2 showing the distribution of responses of focused group discussion for questions 1 to 4 (note: question 4 represents the following: agreed – merit, disagree – politicized)

The above general observations indicate a high level of distrust in the operations and modalities of funding interventions in the university. Many academic staff have lost hope in the process as it seems very difficult to access and less transparent to motivate workers.

Murphy (2004), Otsonu, Asom, Zuwaira, & Olijie, (2016), Gulris & Kamba (2011), Nnadi (2017), Okeke & Eze (2019), Adetola (2014), Mbata (2000), Unachukwu (2009), Famade, Omiyale & Adebola (2015), Manman & Aminu (2014), Immaculata & Victoria (2023), Xi Shi, Patricia, & Peter (2004) believed that a large number of higher educational institution staff lacked the pre- and post-training motivation necessary to encourage trainees to attend training and absorb new information.

When trainees lack sufficient motivation, they will see training negatively, which will deter their eagerness to perform and undermine management's effective training efforts. However, this attitude toward people development commitment might be linked to the institution's administration's incapacity to pick competent workers for training programs and research funds in a transparent and objective manner.

Employees at postsecondary educational institutions are chosen for training based on subjective factors, including regionalism, tribal feelings, and needless favoritism, rather than the organization's and the trainees' objective training evaluation needs. Employees who do not need training are always chosen as a consequence of unethical trainee selection procedures that are based on personal biases and prejudices. Subjective employee selection for training will have a detrimental impact on training intervention plans, preventing them from accomplishing their intended aims and objectives.

Figure 3: Expression of Responses to Group Discussions

Source: Focused Group Discussion (2025).

Figure 3 showing the distribution of responses of focused group discussion for questions 5

Note: Each of the distribution charts was subjected to its proportion on a 100% rating based on the responses observed. Therefore, some staff recommended more than one intervention, which automatically fell within the different distribution proportion as presented on the chart. In summary, a total of 120 responses negated the success of TETFund intervention and manpower development in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus. 67 responses aligned to the success of TETFund intervention and manpower development; 22 responses maintained neutrality of comments, while a total of 61 responses recommended vital areas of intervention to encourage manpower development in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus. The study categorized the responses numerically for the purpose of clarity: Category 1 represents 120 null responses; category 2 represents 67 aligned responses; category 3 of 22 responses symbolizes neutrality of comments, while category 4 observes 61 responses on recommended areas of urgent interventions.

Figure 4: Response Categories on Fund Intervention and Manpower Development

Source: Focused Group Discussion (2025).

Figure 4: showing different category distribution of summarized responses on TETFund Intervention and Manpower Development in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

It can be observed that majority of the academic staff disagreed with the modus operandi and performance of TETFund intervention in the university despite a good number of responses supporting the visibility of the interventions in the welfare of staff. This can be supported by the number of responses suggesting more effective areas these interventions will be better utilized to ascertain improved manpower development. These recommendations and disagreements were born out of consistent failure of the administration to address these concerns, pointing to a certain level of systemic failure. In agreement, Cannel (2004), Fitzgibbons, (2008), Anyadike (2013), Dialoke, Ukah Finian and Ikoro (2016), Nnachi (2009), Rotimi (2005), Igbokwe (2016), Anyim (2014), Omodia (2009), Devi and Shaik (2012), Haslinda (2009) noted that the numerous issues with Nigerian education, which have prevented it from succeeding as the cornerstone of development, include a lack of adequate funding, inadequate classrooms, poor educational infrastructure, a lack of adequate teaching aids like projectors, computers, laboratories, and libraries, a shortage of qualified teachers, and a polluted learning environment. These issues are the result of years of corruption and system failure. Along with these shortcomings, the Nigerian educational system is beset by a host of societal ills, including corruption, cultism, hooliganism, and test fraud. They maintained that the government must re-examine the financial problem, particularly in the areas of infrastructure and research development, if significant progress is to be made in the educational sector. The main obstacles, however, were found to be departmental crises, frequent course allocation changes, admitting unqualified students, inadequate internet facilities, and the difficulty in obtaining a university research scholarship. These issues stem from institutional corruption and inept management. However, administrators in higher education who are tasked with providing leadership and raising the bar for instruction, research, and learning are frequently found abusing their stakeholder privileges to embezzle funds intended for vital areas of research development, which significantly contributes to the decline in staff skill development.

CONCLUSION

Summarily, systemic failure of vital institution of national development in Nigeria has contributed to the rot in the socio-economic and political development in Nigeria. This However, has affected the very fabric of education in Nigeria, encouraging high level of misappropriation, nepotism and total violation of merit system that constitute the base of educational and national development globally. The study interrogated various aspects of TETFund interventions and its impact on manpower development, while examining issues of disbursement and the dynamics of funding staff welfare packages and development programmes in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus, adopting the equity and impartial treatment principles of Adam's Equity theory as a point of analysis. It is deducible from the above analysis that TETFund intervention in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka campus has not been able to encourage manpower development due to inadequate attention to transparency and adherence to meritocracy. Therefore, the study recommends first, a more transparent method of application and disbursement of funds to boost confidence and address grievances of staff who in their majority of 38 responses maintained that the process is politicized. Secondly, encouraging and prioritizing staff development programmes, especially key areas of building and infrastructure, post-graduate programmes, research development and grant., that constitutes the highest staff responses of 8, 10, and 21 respectively.

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